

CLINICAL AND STRUCTURAL CHARACTERISTICS OF CARDIOVASCULAR
PATHOLOGY IN ELDERLY PATIENTS

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Abstract. The study investigated the clinical and demographic characteristics and the structure of cardiovascular diseases in elderly patients. The study was conducted at 7 city clinics in Tashkent and included 300 patients aged 60 to 74 years. An analysis of the prevalence of cardiovascular diseases, their clinical forms, and individual characteristics of disease progression was performed. It was established that arterial hypertension and coronary artery disease were the most common conditions in the structure of cardiovascular pathology. Among the clinical forms of diseases, Grade II arterial hypertension, stable exertional angina pectoris, atrial fibrillation, and NYHA functional class II chronic heart failure predominated. The obtained results reflect the characteristics of the clinical course of cardiovascular diseases in elderly patients.

Keywords: elderly age, cardiovascular diseases, arterial hypertension, coronary artery disease, cardiac arrhythmias, chronic heart failure.

KEKSA YOSHDAGI BEMORLARDA YURAK-QON TOMIR PATOLOGIYASINING
KLINIK VA STRUKTURAVIY TAVSIFI

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Rezume. Tadqiqotda keksa yoshdagi bemorlarda yurak-qon tomir kasalliklarining klinik-demografik xususiyatlari va tuzilmasi o'rganildi. Tadqiqot Tashkent shahridagi 7 ta shahar klinikasi bazasida o'tkazildi va 60 yoshdan 74 yoshgacha bo'lgan 300 nafar bemorni o'z ichiga oldi. Yurak-qon tomir kasalliklarining tarqalishi, ularning klinik shakllari hamda kasallik kechishining ayrim xususiyatlari tahlil qilindi. Yurak-qon tomir patologiyasi tuzilmasida arterial gipertenziya va yurak ishemik kasalligi eng ko'p uchrashi aniqlandi. Kasalliklarning klinik shakllari orasida II darajali arterial gipertenziya, stabil zo'riqish stenokardiyasi, bo'lmachalar fibrillyatsiyasi hamda surunkali yurak yetishmovchiligining II funksional klassi ustunlik qildi. Olingan natijalar keksa yoshdagi bemorlarda yurak-qon tomir kasalliklarining klinik kechish xususiyatlarini aks ettiradi.

Kalit so'zlar: keksa yosh, yurak-qon tomir kasalliklari, arterial gipertenziya, yurak ishemik kasalligi, yurak ritmi buzilishlari, surunkali yurak yetishmovchiligi.

КЛИНИКО-СТРУКТУРНАЯ ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКА СЕРДЕЧНО-СОСУДИСТОЙ
ПАТОЛОГИИ У ПАЦИЕНТОВ ПОЖИЛОГО ВОЗРАСТА

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Резюме. В исследовании изучены клинико-демографические особенности и структура сердечно-сосудистых заболеваний у пациентов пожилого возраста. Исследование проведено на базе 7 городских клиник города Ташкента и включало 300 пациентов в возрасте от 60 до 74 лет. Проведён анализ распространённости сердечно-сосудистых заболеваний, их клинических форм, а также отдельных характеристик течения заболеваний. Установлено, что в структуре сердечно-сосудистой патологии наиболее часто встречались артериальная гипертензия и ишемическая болезнь сердца. Среди клинических форм заболеваний преобладали II степень артериальной гипертензии, стабильная стенокардия напряжения, фибрилляция предсердий и II функциональный класс хронической сердечной недостаточности. Полученные результаты отражают особенности клинического течения сердечно-сосудистых заболеваний у пациентов пожилого возраста.

Ключевые слова: пожилой возраст, сердечно-сосудистые заболевания, артериальная гипертензия, ишемическая болезнь сердца, нарушения ритма сердца, хроническая сердечная недостаточность.

Introduction.

Cardiovascular diseases remain the leading cause of mortality and disability worldwide. According to the World Health Organization, they account for approximately 32% of all deaths, making this group of diseases one of the most significant medical and social problems of modern healthcare [1,2]. The issue is of particular relevance among elderly individuals, since the increase in life expectancy is accompanied by a growing prevalence of chronic cardiovascular diseases [3].

Age-related changes in the cardiovascular system are accompanied by structural and functional remodeling of the myocardium, vascular wall, and cardiac conduction system. This leads to an increased incidence of conditions such as arterial hypertension, coronary artery disease, chronic heart failure, and cardiac arrhythmias [4,5]. It has been established that the prevalence of arterial hypertension among older age groups exceeds 60–70%, which significantly increases the risk of cardiovascular complications [6].

Coronary artery disease also remains one of the most common forms of cardiovascular pathology in elderly patients. According to contemporary epidemiological studies, a considerable proportion of elderly patients present with various clinical forms of myocardial ischemia, including stable angina pectoris and postinfarction atherosclerosis [7]. Cardiac arrhythmias represent another important clinical problem in elderly patients. In particular, atrial fibrillation is considered the most common form of arrhythmia and significantly increases the risk of thromboembolic complications and heart failure [8]. Chronic heart failure, being the final stage of many cardiovascular diseases, is also highly prevalent among elderly patients and is associated with a marked decline in quality of life and an increased risk of hospitalization [9].

In this regard, the study of the structure of cardiovascular diseases and their clinical forms in elderly patients is of great importance for improving the diagnosis, prevention, and treatment of this category of patients [10].

Aim of the study. To investigate the clinical and demographic characteristics, the structure of cardiovascular diseases, and their clinical forms in elderly patients.

Materials and Methods

The study was conducted at 7 city clinics in the Yunusabad district of Tashkent. The study included 300 elderly patients with cardiovascular diseases who underwent examination and treatment at these medical institutions. The age of the patients ranged from 60 to 74 years. A total of 300 elderly patients with various cardiovascular diseases were enrolled in the study. During the investigation, an analysis of the clinical and demographic characteristics of the patients, the structure of cardiovascular pathology, and individual clinical forms of diseases was carried out. The following parameters were evaluated: age and sex of the patients, prevalence of cardiovascular diseases, degree of arterial hypertension, clinical forms of coronary artery disease, types of cardiac arrhythmias, and functional classes of chronic heart failure. Statistical analysis of the obtained data was performed using standard methods of medical statistics. The χ^2 test was applied to assess the significance of differences. Differences were considered statistically significant at $p < 0.05$ (Table 1).

Results of the Study

Table 1

Clinical and Demographic Characteristics of the Examined Patients (n = 300)

Parameter	n	%
Men	162	54.0
Women	138	46.0
Age (years)	67.2 ± 4.1	–
60–64 years	84	28.0
65–69 years	126	42.0
70–74 years	90	30.0

Analysis of the clinical and demographic characteristics of the examined patients showed that the study included 300 elderly individuals. The mean age of the examined patients was 67.2 ± 4.1 years, which corresponds to the elderly age category according to the international classification. In terms of sex distribution, men slightly predominated among the examined patients, accounting for 54.0% (n=162), whereas women constituted 46.0% (n=138). Thus, the ratio of men to women in the study group was relatively balanced, with a slight predominance of the male population.

When distributing patients according to age subgroups, it was established that the largest number of examined patients belonged to the age interval of 65–69 years, accounting for 42.0% (n=126) of the total number of patients. The proportion of patients aged 70–74 years was 30.0% (n=90), whereas the smallest proportion of examined individuals belonged to the 60–64 years age group, comprising 28.0% (n=84). The obtained data indicate that the majority of patients included in the study belonged to the middle segment of the elderly age range, which reflects the characteristic pattern of healthcare utilization among patients with cardiovascular diseases in this age category.

Table 2

Structure of Cardiovascular Diseases in the Examined Patients

Disease	n	%
Coronary artery disease	198	66.0
Arterial hypertension	228	76.0
Chronic heart failure	114	38.0
Cardiac arrhythmias	72	24.0

Analysis of the structure of cardiovascular diseases among the examined patients demonstrated that various forms of cardiovascular pathology characteristic of elderly individuals predominated in the study group (Table 2). Arterial hypertension was the most frequently diagnosed condition among the

examined patients and was identified in 228 individuals, accounting for 76.0% of the total number of patients. Coronary artery disease also occupied a significant place in the structure of the detected pathology and was registered in 198 patients (66.0%). The high prevalence of this disease among the examined patients may be associated with age-related changes in the cardiovascular system and the presence of concomitant risk factors.

Chronic heart failure was identified in 114 patients, accounting for 38.0%. It should be noted that this condition is more often formed as a complication of long-standing cardiovascular diseases, particularly coronary artery disease and arterial hypertension. Cardiac arrhythmias were diagnosed in 72 patients, corresponding to 24.0% of the examined individuals. The development of arrhythmias in elderly patients is often associated with structural and functional changes in the myocardium, as well as with the prolonged course of cardiovascular pathology.

Thus, the obtained results indicate a high prevalence of arterial hypertension and coronary artery disease among elderly patients, confirming the significance of these diseases in the structure of cardiovascular pathology in this category of patients.

Table 3

Structure of Arterial Hypertension in the Examined Patients (n = 228)

Degree of arterial hypertension	n	%	χ^2	p
Grade I	60	26.3		
Grade II	108	47.4		
Grade III	60	26.3	12.48	<0.01

Analysis of the distribution of arterial hypertension grades among the examined patients showed that the largest proportion consisted of patients with Grade II elevation of arterial pressure. This degree of the disease was identified in 108 patients, accounting for 47.4% of the total number of individuals with arterial hypertension. Grade I arterial hypertension was diagnosed in 60 patients (26.3%). A similar proportion of patients was also identified for Grade III disease, which was observed in 60 individuals (26.3%) (Table 3).

The obtained data indicate that in a significant proportion of the examined patients, the disease had already reached the stage of pronounced hemodynamic disturbances. The predominance of Grade II hypertension may be associated with the prolonged course of the disease, age-related changes in the vascular wall, and the presence of concomitant risk factors characteristic of elderly age. Statistical analysis demonstrated the presence of significant differences in the distribution of arterial hypertension grades among the examined patients ($\chi^2 = 12.48$; $p < 0.01$).

Overall, the obtained results reflect the structure of arterial hypertension characteristic of the elderly population, in which moderate and severe forms of elevated arterial pressure are more frequently identified, requiring a comprehensive treatment approach and regular monitoring of hemodynamic parameters.

Table 4

Clinical Forms of Coronary Artery Disease (n = 198)

Form of CAD	n	%	χ^2	p
Stable exertional angina pectoris	90	45.5		
Postinfarction atherosclerosis	66	33.3		

Silent myocardial ischemia	42	21.2	10.27	<0.01
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Analysis of the clinical forms of coronary artery disease among the examined patients demonstrated that chronic forms of myocardial ischemia predominated in the structure of this disease. Stable exertional angina pectoris was the most frequently diagnosed condition, identified in 90 patients and accounting for 45.5% of the total number of patients with coronary artery disease. The second most common form of the disease was postinfarction cardiosclerosis, registered in 66 patients (33.3%) (Table 4).

The presence of this form of coronary artery disease indicates a previous myocardial infarction and reflects the consequences of structural myocardial changes developing during the process of cardiac muscle remodeling. Silent forms of myocardial ischemia were identified in 42 patients, accounting for 21.2%. This variant of the disease is of particular clinical importance because ischemic episodes occur without pronounced pain symptoms and may remain undiagnosed for a long time.

The performed statistical analysis demonstrated significant differences in the distribution of clinical forms of coronary artery disease among the examined patients ($\chi^2 = 10.27$; $p < 0.01$). The obtained results reflect the characteristic structure of coronary artery disease in elderly individuals, in whom chronic forms of coronary pathology predominate.

The conducted statistical analysis also demonstrated significant differences in the distribution of various forms of cardiac arrhythmias among the examined patients ($\chi^2 = 9.36$; $p < 0.01$). The obtained data indicate that atrial fibrillation predominantly occupies the leading position in the structure of arrhythmias in elderly patients, being one of the most common forms of cardiac rhythm disturbances in this age group.

Table 5

Structure of Cardiac Arrhythmias in the Examined Patients (n = 72)

Type of arrhythmia	n	%	χ^2	p
Atrial fibrillation	24	33.3		
Ventricular extrasystole	15	20.8		
Supraventricular extrasystole	12	16.7		
Paroxysmal supraventricular tachycardia	9	12.5		
Atrioventricular block	7	9.7		
Sinus bradycardia	5	7.0	14.26	<0.01

Analysis of the structure of cardiac arrhythmias among the examined patients showed that atrial fibrillation was the most common form among the various arrhythmias. This type of rhythm disturbance was identified in 24 patients, accounting for 33.3% of the total number of patients with arrhythmias (Table 5). The high frequency of atrial fibrillation in elderly individuals may be associated with age-related structural changes in the atrial myocardium, as well as with the prolonged course of cardiovascular diseases. Ventricular extrasystole was diagnosed in 15 patients (20.8%), whereas supraventricular extrasystole was identified in 12 patients (16.7%). These forms of rhythm disturbances are frequently observed in patients with coronary artery disease and may be caused by impaired coronary circulation and electrical instability of the myocardium.

Paroxysmal supraventricular tachycardia was registered in 9 patients, accounting for 12.5% of cases. This rhythm disturbance is characterized by sudden onset and may be accompanied by

hemodynamic deterioration and decreased exercise tolerance. Conduction disturbances in the form of atrioventricular block were identified in 7 patients (9.7%), whereas sinus bradycardia was observed in 5 patients (7.0%). Such changes are more commonly found in elderly patients and may be associated with age-related degeneration of the cardiac conduction system.

Statistical analysis demonstrated significant differences in the distribution of various forms of cardiac arrhythmias among the examined patients ($\chi^2 = 14.26$; $p < 0.01$). The obtained results indicate that atrial fibrillation occupies the leading position in the structure of arrhythmias in elderly patients, whereas other forms of rhythm disturbances occur considerably less frequently.

Table 6

Functional Classes of Chronic Heart Failure (n = 114)

Functional class (NYHA)	n	%	χ^2	p
Class II	54	47.4		
Class III	42	36.8		
Class IV	18	15.8	11.62	<0.01

Analysis of the functional classes of chronic heart failure among the examined patients demonstrated that NYHA functional class II was the most common. This degree of heart failure severity was identified in 54 patients, accounting for 47.4% of the total number of patients with this disease. NYHA functional class III chronic heart failure was diagnosed in 42 patients (36.8%). The presence of this stage of the disease indicates a more pronounced limitation of physical activity and reduced exercise tolerance.

The most severe NYHA functional class IV chronic heart failure was registered in 18 patients, accounting for 15.8%. This category of patients is characterized by significant hemodynamic impairment and the presence of heart failure symptoms even at rest (Table 6).

The performed statistical analysis demonstrated significant differences in the distribution of chronic heart failure functional classes among the examined patients ($\chi^2 = 11.62$; $p < 0.01$). The obtained results indicate that moderately severe forms of chronic heart failure predominated in the studied group of elderly patients, whereas severe stages of the disease were observed considerably less frequently.

Conclusion. The conducted study demonstrated that cardiovascular diseases in elderly patients are characterized by a high prevalence and a wide variety of clinical forms. In the structure of cardiovascular pathology, arterial hypertension and coronary artery disease were the most frequently identified conditions. Among patients with arterial hypertension, Grade II disease predominated. In the structure of coronary artery disease, stable exertional angina pectoris was the most common clinical form. Among cardiac rhythm disturbances, atrial fibrillation occupied the leading position. Analysis of the functional classes of chronic heart failure demonstrated the predominance of NYHA functional class II.

The obtained results reflect the characteristics of the clinical course of cardiovascular pathology in elderly patients and may be used to improve diagnostic approaches and optimize therapeutic measures in this category of patients.

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